

Mechanisms of backward wave propagation due to internal excitation in a passive 3D model of the human ear

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Abstract. Otoacoustic emissions, which are sounds generated inside the cochlea owing primarily to non-linearities, have been widely used in auditory diagnosis. However, their generation and backward propagation mechanisms inside the cochlea are not entirely understood. The discussion focuses on distortion product otoacoustic emissions. Two theories are debated for the mechanism of backward propagation of distortion products. According to the traveling-wave theory, the distortion products propagate backwards along the basilar membrane (BM) as a fluid-structure coupled traveling wave. On the other hand, the compression-wave theory proposes that distortion products propagate backward via fluid as compression waves. To address this debate, the current study delves into the acoustic pathways of energy transfer from inside the cochlea to the outer ear using a symmetric tapered duct 3D finite element (FE) passive human ear cochlear model. The model includes a flexible orthotropic plate that separates the two ducts without restricting its number of radial modes. The study examines the basilar membrane response to a specific input at a localized area via internal excitation. It is observed that in response to acoustic stimuli, compression waves can excite the basilar membrane, but its effect is overshadowed by the larger traveling wave near the best frequency. When internal excitation occurs basal to the best place of the stimulus frequency, the amplitude decreases towards the stapes with a constant phase slope, indicating a standing wave. Conversely, apical to the forcing location, the BM amplitude peaks at the best place, similar to the acoustically induced response. The phase slope is relatively similar to that of acoustic stimulation with a phase offset, suggesting a forward-traveling wave.

INTRODUCTION

Kemp's [1] discoveries highlighted the cochlea's ability to produce sounds transmitted through the middle ear as otoacoustic emissions (OAEs), suggesting a link to cochlear health. OAEs are valuable for diagnosing auditory disorders and studying cochlear physiology, yet their mechanisms remain unclear, limiting their applications. Two theories have been proposed on how OAEs propagate backwards inside the cochlea. One theory suggests backward-traveling waves (slow mode), while the other suggests compression waves (fast mode) in cochlear fluids. Backward waves, initially proposed by Kemp [2], imply a delay mirroring forward propagation. However, direct evidence from basilar membrane measurements is lacking, with conflicting findings sparking debates on cochlear sound propagation mechanisms [3].

The compression mode aligns closely with stapes movement, exhibiting swift changes within the cochlear environment [4, 5]. While its impact on sensory tissue motion is minimal under typical circumstances, it can induce notable movements. The movements possess the potential to activate hair cells and initiate responses in the auditory nerve, especially at higher stimulus intensities [6]. Conversely, the slow mode, characterized by the fluid-structure coupled traveling wave pressure, entails gradual pressure variations propagating along the basilar membrane (BM) [7]. This mode emerges from the intricate interplay between the elasticity of the cochlear partition and the inertia of fluid, primarily the BM. As a result, a traveling wave forms, serving as a conduit for sound energy propagation throughout the cochlea. Notably, the pressure within the partition lags behind that of the stapes by several cycles [4]. This mode plays a pivotal role in driving the motion of the BM and stimulating auditory nerve fibers. Furthermore, it is augmented by the cochlear amplifier, a mechanism involving active feedback from outer hair cells (OHCs). This amplification process enhances sensitivity and frequency selectivity within the auditory system. Interestingly, while the cochlear amplifier appears to bypass amplifying fast-mode motions, its function appears intricately linked to the wavelength of the traveling wave for effective amplification [8]. The propagation direction of OAEs through the cochlea, whether via fast mode, slow mode, or both, has long puzzled researchers in cochlear mechanics. A fundamental query remains: how and if compression waves can excite the BM.

This study aims to explore the primary mechanism of reverse wave propagation in the cochlea. Vibroacoustic simulations of a 3D FE passive human ear model are conducted in ACTRAN[®] software. We have expanded upon our previous model [9] of the passive human cochlea by incorporating a FE middle ear model. The replication of the traveling wave (TW) effect in the cochlea, with various parameters such as middle ear pressure gain, BM velocity, and cochlear pressure are benchmarked against experimental results from human cadaver ears. Active cochlear amplification mechanisms are omitted in this study.

FIGURE 1: The detailed FE model of the human ear is depicted in Figure. (a) It comprises a FE mesh model of the human cochlea, featuring tapered straight symmetric ducts and the BM (b) The FE model of the human middle-ear structure includes the tympanic membrane (TM), ossicles, ligaments, and tendons. Notably, the model does not incorporate the air volumes of the ear canal and the middle ear cavity. (c) The complete human ear FE mesh model is shown.

MODEL AND METHODS

Finite element model of the middle ear

The geometry of the human middle ear is derived from a micro-computer tomography (CT) scan of a fresh frozen human temporal bone conducted by the Biophysics and Bio-Medical Physics research group at the University of Antwerp [10]. The geometric structure obtained from this source is then imported into HyperMesh[®] software for meshing, resulting in a corresponding finite element mesh model. Subsequently, the meshed model is transferred into ACTRAN[®] software for finite element analysis.

Figure 1(B) illustrates the interconnected 3D structure of the finite element model, with various components labeled, including the tympanic membrane (TM), umbo, tympani maller connection (TMC), malleus, anterior malleolar ligament (AML), incudo-malleolar joint (IMJ), incus, incudo-stapedial joint (ISJ), stapes, stapes footplate (FP), stapes annular ligament (SAL), tensor-tympani tendon (TTT), lateral malleolar ligament (LML), and posterior incus ligament (PIL). The tympanic membrane is meshed using three-noded solid elements, with a total of 16945 elements. The model incorporates frequency-dependent loss factors for the TM, and the damping coefficient for the three ossicles (malleus, incus, and stapes) is set at 1%, with a Young's modulus value of 14.1 GPa. The density of each ossicle is derived from measurements on temporal bones reported by Sim et al. (2007) [11]. Soft structures such as IMJ, ISJ, LML, TTT, TMC, and SAL are assigned Young's moduli with complex values, incorporating both stiffness and damping. It is important to note that the loss factor varies with frequency. Both IMJ and ISJ are meshed as solid domains. The middle ear model [12, 13] includes the fixed outer ends of the TT, AML, LML, and PIL, as well as the fixed outer edges of the SAL. The material properties of the different components of the middle ear are taken from various literature [14, 15, 16].

Finite element model of the inner ear

Figure 1(A) presents a detailed depiction of the un-coiled symmetric human cochlear model dimensions whose cross-sectional area and boundary conditions are utilized in this study. While a comprehensive description of the passive inner ear model is available in our previous work [9], a brief description is given next. The human cochlea, characterized by its spiral shape with two and a half turns, comprises three fluid-filled channels: the scala vestibuli (SV),

scala media (SM), and scala tympani (ST). The cochlea is depicted as a tapered straight duct which is filled with incompressible fluid and surrounded by rigid walls. The SV and ST ducts are divided by an elastic, orthotropic plate, forming the basilar membrane (BM). For simplicity, the SM duct and the micro-structure of the organ of Corti (OoC) have been omitted from this study. The BM, tapering in shape, is divided into 14 equidistant sections from base to apex, with Young's modulus data obtained from Kim's cochlear model [17] showing a consistent decrease along its length. The primary orthotropic axes align with the length and width of the BM. The cochlear duct spans 35 mm in length, with the helicotrema covering 2 mm. Cross-sectional areas of the SV, ST, and BM vary with distance from the stapes. The model incorporates 30% structural damping for the BM, and the fluid within the SV and ST is taken as water, with a fixed speed of sound at 1,500 m/s. A 10% loss factor is also applied to account for fluid viscosity losses. Refer to Tables 1 and 2 in our prior study [9] for further details on the symmetric cochlear duct dimensions and other BM and cochlear fluid parameters.

By integrating both the middle ear and inner ear models, the FE model's frequency response is acquired using ACTRAN[®] software. The impulse response is derived by employing Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) techniques on the frequency response data. During the acoustic stimulation, a pressure of 90 dB SPL is exerted on the tympanic membrane. Conversely, equivalent pressure (considering an average middle ear gain of 25 dB) is applied at the designated excitation location in internal excitation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The responses of the middle ear, basilar membrane (BM), and fluid pressures within the scala vestibuli (SV) and scala tympani (ST) are predicted in response to the following two stimuli. The investigation comprises two primary components:

- (a) Acoustic stimuli at the ear canal: 90 dB SPL applied directly to the tympanic membrane.
- (b) Internal excitation on the BM: Uniform force per unit area is applied on the BM across the width and over a longitudinal span of 280 micrometres centered at 17 mm location from the base.

Acoustic stimuli at the ear canal

For this case, the results are benchmarked with experimental data from the literature. The predicted middle ear pressure gain (MEPG) given by P_{SV}/P_{EC} is shown in Figure 2 (a & b). MEPG has a distinctive bandpass characteristic with a peak at 1 kHz, with both rise and fall at the rate of 20 dB/decade, and a concomitant phase. These findings agree well with previously published data by Aibara et al. (2001) [18], Puria et al. (1997) [19], Nakajima et al. (2009) [6], and Zhang et al. (2020) [20].

Figure 2 (c & d) shows the predicted BM velocity relative to stapes V_{BM}/V_{OW} for 12 mm position from the base. The best frequency is ~ 3.5 kHz, with the phase indicating the traveling wave. The predictions agree well with the model of Kim et al. [17] and with experiments from Gundersen et al. [21] and Stenfelt et al. [22].

Traveling (slow) vs. compression (fast) wave components

Basis for compression mode excitation of the BM

The waves launched by a piston in an acoustic duct propagate as compression waves, with longitudinal acoustic modes occurring under certain frequency conditions [23]. In the cochlea, the stapes act like this piston, whereas the flexible BM influences these longitudinal compression modes, altering their resonance frequencies and shapes. Examining a hypothetical scenario with a rigid BM, resonance frequencies for symmetric longitudinal modes in a bent-around cochlear duct with the pressure-release condition at the round window are calculated for an overall length $L = 70\text{mm}$. The resonance frequencies of the first three modes are 10.14 kHz, 30.4 kHz, and 50.7 kHz by using the relation $[f_n = \frac{nc}{2L}]$, while the corresponding mode shapes can be obtained by the relation $[\sin(\frac{n\pi x}{L})]$. As frequency approaches 10 kHz, pressure gradients begin to manifest in the human cochlear duct, including pressure difference in the SV duct versus the ST duct across the BM. This $(P_{SV} - P_{ST})$ pressure difference is capable of driving the BM. Some experimental observations [4, 24] also suggest that BM vibrations can be excited by compression waves, particularly evident above 10 kHz. In Figure 3 (a & b), above this frequency (10 kHz), the BM velocity induced by compression waves becomes apparent alongside the smaller traveling wave component of BM velocity. Experimental findings in rodent cochlea have reported the ability of compression wave to excite BM vibrations [4]. The vertical lines in Figure 3 (a & b) mark the three (modal) frequencies.

FIGURE 2: In the first row, (a) magnitude & (b) phase of the ME gain derived from the FE model, compared with data published by Aibara et al. (2001), Puria et al. (1997), Nakajima et al. (2009), and Zhang et al. (2020). In the second row, plots depict (a) magnitude & (b) phase of BM velocity normalized by oval window velocity $[V_{BM}/V_{OW}]$ at 12 mm from the base. Plots display results for two distinct damping loss factors: 10% and 30%. The FE model results are compared with experimental data from Gundersen (1978), Stenfelt (2003) and Kim's (2011) model simulation.

FIGURE 3: In the first column, (a) magnitude & (b) phase of BM velocity re stapes plotted at 12 mm from the base for two cases, $c = 1500$ m/sec and $c = \text{infinite}$. In the second and third columns, the pressure profiles of SV & ST ducts for flexible BM under two conditions: (c) $c = 1500$ m/s, and (d) $c = \text{infinite}$. (' c ' is the speed of sound).

Simulations done to show compression mode excitation of the BM

To highlight the excitation of the BM by compression modes, the simulations here extend to 60 kHz. The resonance frequencies of longitudinal compression modes are observed, which are 14.5 kHz, 32.5 kHz, and 55.0 kHz, with shifts due to BM flexibility and the presence of the helicotrema. Figure 3 (c) depicts pressure profiles along the cochlear length, showing resonances of longitudinal compression modes. However, the presence of the helicotrema suppresses certain modes, as seen in the absence of the first anti-symmetric mode at 22 kHz. Simulations with infinite speed of sound illustrate the removal of compression mode effects, resulting in a flat pressure profile. (See Figure 3 (d)). Two important observations to highlight here are that (a) compression waves do indeed excite the BM, and (b) BM vibration from compression mode can be significant at locations apical to the BP

Internal excitation of the BM at 17 mm position

The normalized responses of stapes displacement for BM internal excitation and the BM displacement for stapes excitation appear identical in the time domain (Figure 4 (a)). This result may be expected owing to structural-acoustic reciprocity within a passive system [25]. However, some differences are observed at high frequencies when the same data is represented in the frequency domain (Figure 4 (b & c)). This finding needs to be investigated further.

FIGURE 4: (a) Impulse responses of the BM (at 17mm) and stapes (when input at BM 17 mm) are plotted for acoustic stimuli and internal excitation, respectively. Each response is normalized to its respective maximum value. Panels (b) magnitude and (c) phase of normalized volume velocity of BM and stapes per unit pressure are plotted across the frequency range for acoustic stimuli and internal excitation, respectively.

Spatial response of the basilar membrane

The spatial pattern of BM velocity is illustrated in Figure 5 at a low frequency (500 Hz), with the best place ~ 26 mm; the figure is plotted to assess the direction of wave propagation in the cochlea during internal excitation. Note that the location of internal excitation is at 17 mm with best frequency of 1660 Hz.

In Figure 5, black lines show BM responses to internal excitation at 500 Hz, while red lines show responses to acoustic stimuli at the same frequency. Figure 5 (a) depicts the BM vibration when the BP is apical to the excitation place and amplitude of BM decreases toward the stapes from the basal side of the excitation, with a constant phase slope, indicating a standing wave (see Figure 5 (b)). On the apical side of the excitation, amplitude of BM peaks at the BP, mirroring the acoustic response but with a 250° phase offset. So, when internal excitation is basal to the BP of stimulus frequency, a forward traveling wave with a slope of phase akin to acoustic stimulation emerges. These observations agree with Li and Grosh (2012) [26] and de Boer et al. (2007) [27].

Similar BM responses are observed at frequencies of 6010 Hz and 1660 Hz, corresponding to best places at ~ 8.5 mm and ~ 17 mm, respectively (plots not included). At an excitation frequency of 6010 Hz, a gradual decrease in BM amplitude toward the stapes is noted, accompanied by a phase response characterized by a slight backward-wave slope. This response is significantly influenced by evanescent decay, diverging from acoustic stimulation, as observed similarly by Li and Grosh (2012) [26].

Figure 6 illustrates the difference in scala fluid pressure relative to stapes pressure for two different excitation methods: internal excitation and acoustic stimuli at 1 kHz, 5 kHz and 14.5 kHz frequencies. It can be observed that, as we move from base to apex, the fluid pressure difference becomes zero beyond the best place (~ 21 mm) in the case of 1 kHz for both acoustic and internal excitation scenarios. Conversely, in the case of 5 kHz (with the BP at ~ 12 mm) and 14.5 kHz (with the BP at ~ 4.6 mm), the fluid pressure difference locally increases at the internal excitation location, i.e., both the ST pressure (P_{ST}) and SV pressure (P_{SV}) are equal (opposite sign) to each other and locally influenced by excitation. Spatial SV and ST pressure plots in the cochlea show that acoustic stimulation produces symmetric pressure levels on the other hand of traveling-wave pressure, whereas internal excitation results in minimal symmetric pressure (figure not shown).

FIGURE 6: (Shown in color online) illustrates the normalized fluid pressure difference of two ducts (SV & ST) for three different excitations at (a) 1 kHz, (b) 5 kHz and (c) 14.5 kHz. Each response has been normalized relative to its own maximum value.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, a comprehensive model of a passive straight-tapered cochlea of the human ear is developed, incorporating the compressible middle ear, perilymph-filled scala vestibuli, scala tympani, helicotrema, and BM. Special attention is given to modeling the BM, with its width increasing linearly as its thickness decreases from the base to the apex without limiting its number of radial modes. Vibroacoustic simulation of the model is conducted, and the results of the passive model are validated with available FE models and measured data on human cadavers available in the literature. Following this, internal excitation on the BM is simulated to examine the resulting direction of wave propagation within the cochlea.

In response to acoustic stimuli, the model predictions agree with Olson's 2013 findings [4], showing that compression wave is capable of exciting the BM, albeit overshadowed by the larger traveling wave near the BF. The analysis extended to high frequencies illustrates the occurrence of longitudinal compression mode resonances, with the modal effects disappearing when infinite speed of sound is assumed. For internal excitation, if the location of excitation

FIGURE 5: BM responses to internal excitation and acoustic stimuli are plotted for a frequency of 500 Hz. Panels (a) and (b) represent BM amplitudes and phases. Both amplitude and phase values are normalized relative to the stapes.

is basal to the BP of the stimulus frequency, an amplitude decrease towards the stapes is observed, and the overall response mimics a forward-traveling wave with a phase slope akin to the case of acoustic stimulation.

This model will be used as a foundation to study the nature of waves generated by internal excitation of the BM, extending up to high frequencies. Further investigations will delve into the intricacies of the BM interaction with compression and traveling waves, aimed at understanding how the cochlea emits sound.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Ales, Vetesnik]: Thank you very much for your interesting contribution that deals with propagation mechanisms of OAEs. The article is written in a comprehensible way, the results are presented very well. I have following comments:

1. In Abstract: first sentence: "Otoacoustic emissions...to non-linearities," I think that for the generation of OAEs is not necessary non-linearity, SFOAE are assumed to be due to a linear reflections, spontaneous emission due to an instability of cochlear amplifier.
2. last sentence: you write: "a phase slope similar to acoustic stimulation." Referring to Fig.5b, the phase for internal excitation is constant on the interval 0-17 mm, different from the phase of phase elicited by acoustical stimuli.
3. Would be possible to provide definitions/explanations for "structural damping for the BM", " loss factor" and "the pressure-release condition at the round window". What do you mean by " pressure gradients", the first derivative with respect to space?
4. Fig. 5: I interpret result for internal excitation as standing wave on the interval (0,17) (your phase is constant) and traveling on the remaining interval. Your results corresponds to analysis performed using 2D model assuming incompressible fluid, Vetešník and Gummer [J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 131, 3914–3934 (2012)].

[Vikas, Lakhmani]: Thank you very much for your thoughtful feedback and kind words regarding my article. I am pleased to hear that you found the article comprehensible and that the results were well-presented. Please find my responses to each of your comments below:

1. While SFOAE is usually considered to be due to linear reflections, nonlinear effects have also been observed in SFOAE. For example, See Walsh *et al.* (2010) and Goodman *et al.* (2003). Nevertheless, please note the first sentence edited in the abstract.
2. Thank you for pointing that out. In the updated manuscript, the lines have been revised.
3. Sure, here are the definitions and explanations for each term:
 - (a) **Structural damping for the BM:** Structural damping refers to the inherent energy dissipation characteristics of a structure when it vibrates. The effects of shear viscosity at the interfaces between solids and viscous fluids are not captured by the elements used in the present FE software. To compensate for those factors, we have used a structural damping factor of 0.3 for the BM. This damping is crucial for mimicking the amplitude of vibrations similar to measurements.
 - (b) **Loss factor:** To introduce the viscous losses in the fluid, a loss factor of 0.1 was applied by adjusting the speed of sound in the fluid, referred to as the complex speed of sound. i.e. $(1500 + 150i)$ m/s. For more details please refer, *Kinsler and Frey, Fundamentals of acoustics, 4 ed. Wiley, 2000. [23]*
 - (c) **Pressure-release condition at the Round Window:** The pressure-release boundary condition in acoustics refers to zero acoustic pressure at the boundary. Since the round window membrane is very flexible (and it faces air on the other side), its mechanical impedance is neglected, which effectively leads to a pressure-release boundary condition. For more details please refer, *Kinsler and Frey, Fundamentals of acoustics, 4 ed. Wiley, 2000. [23]*
 - (d) **Pressure gradients:** Pressure gradients refer to the rate of change of pressure with respect to space. Mathematically, the pressure gradient in one dimension can be expressed as:

$$\nabla P = \frac{\partial P}{\partial x}$$

where: ∇P is the pressure gradient, ∂P is the pressure, and ∂x is the spatial coordinate.

4. Thank you for your insightful interpretation. It is observed from Figure 5 that when internal excitation occurs basal to the best place of the stimulus frequency, a decrease in amplitude towards the stapes with a constant phase slope is observed, indicating a standing wave. Conversely, apical to the forcing location, the BM amplitude is observed to peak at the best place, similar to the acoustically induced response. The phase slope is found

to be relatively similar to that of acoustic stimulation, with a phase offset, suggesting a forward-traveling wave. Yes, the observed results are quite similar to the findings of Vetešník and Gummer [J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 131, 3914–3934 (2012)].

[Sridhar, Krishnamurti]: Very interesting study! Your poster is well-organized and clearly written. I have a question about the anti-symmetric mode. Why is the first anti-symmetric longitudinal compression mode not visible in Figure 3(c)?

[Vikas, Lakhmani]: Thank you Prof. Sridhar. The first anti-symmetric longitudinal compression mode $[\sin(\frac{2\pi x}{L})]$, if present, would be expected at **20.28 kHz** with nodes at the helicotrema, stapes, & round-window and antinode at the middle of the BM (about 13 mm from the base). However, the presence of helicotrema subsides this mode, and thus the $[\sin(\frac{2\pi x}{L})]$ is not seen at **22 kHz**.

[Ondřej, Klimeš]: Interesting poster and concept of study. I have a question regarding the boundary conditions. What boundary conditions were used in the FE model during the simulation?

[Vikas, Lakhmani]: Thank you, Ondřej. The boundary conditions used in the FE model during the simulation were:

- (a) For acoustic stimuli at the ear canal: 90 dB SPL is applied directly to the tympanic membrane. For internal excitation on the BM, uniform force per unit area is applied on the BM across the width and over a longitudinal span of 280 micrometers centered at a 17 mm location from the base.
- (b) In the middle ear: fixed outer ends of the TT, AML, LML, and PIL. Also fixed outer edges of the SAL.
- (c) The fluid-structure interaction (FSI) coupling is established between the BM and the cochlear fluid.
- (d) SV and ST duct pressure is equal at helicotrema.
- (e) Pressure-release boundary condition is applied at a round window.

For more details, please refer *Lakhmani et al., vol. 268, no. 4, pp. 4585–4596, (2023)*, [Vibroacoustic simulations of asymmetric tapered duct mimicking cochlear hydrodynamics] [9]
